

MATERIALS SCIENCE AND MECHANICS OF MACHINES

RECOMMENDATIONS FOR MANUFACTURING PARTS OF WORM AND HEALTH-WORM REDUCERS

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Abstract

This article examines the most effective developments that they are developed and produced as an effective alternative to conventional standard worm gearboxes Ч-50, 2Ч-63, 2Ч-80, Ч-80, Ч-100, Ч-125 and ЦЧ-160-50, still widely in demand on the international gear market.

Keywords: worm shaft, gears, output shaft gear ratio, worm shaft lifting angle, modular thread.

We will illustrate the design features of these gearboxes and their main operational advantages compared to worm gear units with an example. Let's consider three gearboxes: worm gearbox 2Ч-80, Ч-160-50 and cylindrical worm gearbox ЦЧ-160-50, table №1 shows their technical characteristics. In the Ч-160-50 gearbox, the required gear ratio $i=50$ is ensured by using a worm gear with a single-thread worm $Z_1=1$ and a worm wheel with a number of teeth $Z_2=50$, $m=5$ mm. At a worm rotation speed $n_1=1500$ min, its peripheral speed is 4,7 m/s, which significantly affects the wear rate of the wheel teeth and the thermal power of the gearbox. The permissible transmitted torque of such a gearbox is $T_2 = 1180$ N·m, and efficiency (КПД) = 0,75.

In the design of the ЦЧ-160-50 gearbox, the same gear ratio $i_{общ}=50$ is obtained using a worm gear $i_ч = 16$ with a double-thrust worm $Z_1=2$, number of wheel teeth $Z_2=32$, module $m=8$ and a high-speed spur gear with $i_ц=3,15$. The cylindrical stage of such a gearbox, with a constant input shaft rotation speed n

= 1500 min, reduces the worm rotation speed to 476 min, and its peripheral speed to 1,49 m/s. With a reduced worm speed, the wear rate of the wheel teeth is noticeably reduced, which makes it possible to increase the thermal power of the gearbox and the permissible transmitted torque to $T_2=2000$ Н·м.

In this case, the efficiency of one input worm gear with $i_ч=16$ is 0,85. In general, taking into account losses in the cylindrical stage, the overall efficiency of the 2Ч-80 gearbox is 0,83, which is 8% higher than that of the standard Ч-160-50 gearbox. What can consumers choose? Consumers using helical-worm gearboxes can solve a variety of operational problems. Let's characterize them.

1. Increased service life

We consider this operational property to be the most important advantage for the majority of consumers of helical-worm gearboxes. The point is, first of all, that the most significant disadvantage of conventional worm gearboxes is their very limited service life. The values of the nominal transmitted torque of a conventional worm gearbox, entered in its passport, correspond to the maximum permissible value of its thermal power (at $t_{oil}=95^\circ\text{C}$).

Table 1.

Technical characteristics of gearboxes

Standard size	$i_{общ}$	$i_ч$	$i_ц$	$m_ч$	$Z_ч$	T_2 Н·М	Resource, hour	Efficiency (КПД)
2Ч-80	8-80	-	-	3	36	200-280	8890	0,90
Ч160-50	50	50	-	5	50	1180	10000	0,75
ЦЧ-160-50	50	16	3,15	8	32	2000	25000	0,83

Therefore, any excess operating loads caused by changes in technological processes lead to overheating of the gearbox ($t_{oil}=95^\circ\text{C}$), associated with an increase in the rate of tooth wear, is not observed (since

it has a significantly higher reserve of permissible thermal power). Therefore, when operated at loads less than the maximum permissible, such a gearbox will have a significantly increased service life, the minimum value of which can be determined by the approximate formula:

$$L_{\Pi\Upsilon} = \left(\frac{T_{2\Pi\Upsilon}}{T_{2\Upsilon}} \right) \cdot L_{\Upsilon} \quad (1)$$

$L_{\Pi\Upsilon}$ – service life of a worm-cylinder gearbox;

L_{Υ} – service life of the worm gearbox;

$L_{2\Pi\Upsilon}$ - rated torque according to the passport of the worm-cylinder gearbox;

$T_{2\Upsilon}$ – is the actual torque transmitted by the helical-worm gearbox and corresponding to the rated torque according to the worm gearbox's passport.

2. Increased efficiency and energy cost savings

The use of worm gears with a reduced gear ratio in helical-worm gearboxes ensures a stable increase in the efficiency of the gearbox. Moreover, this operational effect, important for consumers, increases with increasing gear ratio (see Table 2). Increased operational reliability and cost savings associated with downtime of process equipment, repair and replacement of the worm drive.

Successful operating practice has shown high reliability and accident-free operation of helical-worm

gearboxes in reversible mechanisms with frequent starts and stops, in drives with shock loads and increased starting torques (for example, in extruders, mills, mixers). Conventional worm gearboxes previously used in such equipment often failed and their replacement led to significant downtime of process equipment and losses.

3. Reducing the weight and dimensions of the drive

When choosing helical-worm gearboxes instead of worm gearboxes, the weight and dimensions of the drive can be significantly reduced. For example, to transmit a torque of 2000 N•m on the output shaft, a $\Pi\Upsilon$ -160-50 gearbox (weight 230 kg) or a Υ -200-50 worm gearbox (weight 350 kg) is required. Obviously, the use of $\Pi\Upsilon$ -160-50 instead of Υ -200-50 makes it possible to make the drive more compact, its weight will be 120 kg less. At the same time, the cost of $\Pi\Upsilon$ -160-50 will be less than the cost of Υ -200-50. The described advantages of $\Pi\Upsilon$ and $\Pi\Pi\Upsilon$ gearboxes will be appreciated primarily by those consumers who care about saving their money and strive to produce equipment that can compete with foreign analogues.

Table 2.

Technical characteristics of reducers

Standard size	Gear ratio, i								
	16	20	25	31,5	40	50	63	80	
	reducers efficiency								
1.	2 Υ -80	-	-	-	-	0,72	0,71	0,64	0,61
2.	$\Pi\Upsilon$ -40	0,81	0,77	0,75	0,75	0,74	0,74	0,73	0,72
3.	Υ -160	0,90	0,87	0,86	0,83	0,79	0,75	0,74	0,69
4.	$\Pi\Upsilon$ -160	0,90	0,88	0,87	0,85	0,84	0,83	0,82	0,81

Table 3.

Standard size	Gear ratio	Output torque T_2 Nm	Radial load on output shaft N	Efficiency (КПД)	Total weight, kg
1.	2 Υ -80	200-280	4000	0,61-0,90	25
2.	$\Pi\Upsilon$ -40	28-37	1300	0,64-0,91	43
3.	Υ -160	1100-1900	15000	0,64-0,92	155
4.	$\Pi\Upsilon$ -160	1500-3000	11000	0,64-0,97	157

To construct a kinematic diagram for calculating the rotation of the device drive, it is recommended to use kinematic symbols in accordance with GOST 2.770-68. The rotating movement will start from the drive electric motor and is transmitted to the working

part of the device through a flexible coupling half, which is controlled during manufacturing in accordance with ГОСТ P 50371–92, positions No. 53 and No. 84.

1-fig. General view of reducers
Mechanical properties of gears

Gear materials	Methods of pouring liquid metal for the manufacture of gears.	Mechanical properties	
		σ_v	σ_T
БрО10НФ	Centrifugal method	285	165
БрО10Ф	Sand method	275	200
		230	140
БрО5Ц5С5	Sand method	200	90
		145	80

To determine the parameters of the teeth, we take an example based on the 2Ч-80 gearbox, according to the given formula (2) we carry out the calculation for the crown teeth using the following formula.

$$m = \frac{2 \cdot a_w}{q + z_2} = \frac{2 \cdot 80}{13 + 40} = 3; \quad (2)$$

$$m = (1,5 \dots 1,7) \cdot \frac{a_w}{z_2} = \frac{1,5 \cdot 80}{40} = 3; \quad (3)$$

m-module;

a_w - center distance;

q - angle of inclination of teeth;

Z_2 - number of driven gear teeth.

To determine the pitch diameter of the worm shaft of gearboxes as the ostial one, we take an example also based on the 2Ч-80 gearbox and, according to formula (4), we carry out calculations to determine the pitch diameter of the worm shaft.

$$d_1 = m \cdot q = 3 \cdot 13 = 39; \quad (4)$$

To determine the outer diameter of the worm shaft of any worm gearboxes, we make calculations using the following formula:

$$h_1 = m \cdot q = 3 \cdot 0,99708 + 39 = 42; \quad (5)$$

To determine the angle of inclination of the teeth of the worm shaft, we take tabular data No. 5, according to the tabular data we find q-13 and determine the angle of inclination of the grooves $4^{\circ}23'55''$.

Table 5.

Table for determining the rise of coal turns

Z	q					
	8	9	10	11	12	13
1	$7^{\circ}07'30''$	$6^{\circ}20'25''$	$5^{\circ}42'38''$	$5^{\circ}11'40''$	$4^{\circ}59'49''$	$4^{\circ}23'55''$
2	$14^{\circ}02'11''$	$12^{\circ}31'44''$	$11^{\circ}18'17''$	$10^{\circ}18'47''$	$9^{\circ}27'44''$	$8^{\circ}44'46''$
3	$20^{\circ}33'22''$	$18^{\circ}26'06''$	$16^{\circ}41'57''$	$15^{\circ}15'18''$	$14^{\circ}02'10''$	$12^{\circ}59'40''$
4	$26^{\circ}33'00''$	$23^{\circ}57'00''$	$24^{\circ}48'00''$	$19^{\circ}58'59''$	$18^{\circ}26'06''$	$17^{\circ}06'10''$

To determine the calculation of the gear ratio U of the output shaft, the following formulas are recommended:

$$U = \frac{n_{input\ shaft}}{n_{output\ shaft}} = \frac{1000}{40} = 250 \text{ об/мин}; \quad (6)$$

$n_{input\ shaft}$ - electric motor rotation speed;

$n_{output\ shaft}$ - reducers output shaft speed.

For all gearboxes, it is recommended to make worm shaft journals for settling the coupling half in accordance with ГОСТ 27701-88, Fig. 2.

2-fig. Input shaft journals for all gearboxes in accordance with ГОСТ P 50371-92, version No. 84.

3-fig. The input shaft coupling halves for all gearboxes are manufactured in accordance with GOST P 50371–92, version No. 84.

4-fig. The output shaft coupling halves for all gearboxes are manufactured in accordance with GOST P 50371–92, version No. 84.

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